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SHARED CHALLENGES OF HPV DRIVEN CANCERS FROM RESEARCH TO PRACTICE

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ABSTRACTS

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Geotropism and oncogenic potential of HPV infections in cohort study populations in Vojvodina, north region of Serbia

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03 - Epidemiology and natural history

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Background/Objectives: This study evaluates the prevalence of HPV infection in women from Vojvodina, north part of Serbia, according to cytological status and pathological changes of cervix, dysplasia and cancer. According to current estimates in Serbia, 1327 women get cervical cancer every year, and 551 die from cervical cancer. Cervical cancer is the 4th most common cancer among women in Serbia and the second most common cancer among women between the ages of 15 and 44. The aim of this study was to examine the prevalence and distribution of different HPV genotypes in a cohort of female patients with normal cytological findings, as well as the oncogenic potential of HPV infection genotypes in a group of female patients with histopathologically verified dysplasia and cervical cancer in Vojvodina, the northern region of Serbia.

Methods: The research was conducted as a retrospective study at the Oncology Institute of Vojvodina (IOV) and the Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina (IZJZV). It used data from the medical records of female patients treated for cervical intraepithelial neoplasia or cervical cancer at the Department of Gynecology, Clinic for Surgical Oncology, Oncology Institute of Vojvodina in Sremska Kamenica in the period from 2016 to 2021, as well as the laboratory findings of the IZJZV for a group of female patients with normal cytological results of the Papanikolau (PAPA) smear. The source of the material was the archival material of the IOV and IZJZV obtained from the medical documentation on the histopathological material from operation and cytological findings, the identified genotypes of the

HPV and the age of the female patients. A total of 740 women, ranging from 20 to 82 years of age, with different cytological results were enrolled. 576 samples were classified as NILM, while 164 samples belong to a group of abnormal histopathology (LSIL/HSIL/cervical cancer). The HPV genotyping assay was performed using the EUROArray HPV test to detect 30 HPV genotypes.

Results: Twelve HPV genotypes classified as carcinogenic to humans were detected in 252 (55%) of NILM samples, while the same genotypes were detected in 125 samples (76.2%) classified as LSIL/HSIL/cervical cancer. In our study, the most prevalent genotypes were HPV 16, 31, 53, 51, and 18 in NILM cytological status. In the samples with the abnormal histopathology, the most prevalent genotypes were HPV 16, 33, 31, and 56, while 18 and 39 were equally verified. Genotype 16 was the most prevalent in the examined sample, with a higher prevalence in higher-grade histopathological findings: 18.8% in LSIL, 31.9% in HSIL, and 75% in cervical cancer samples. Infection with multiple associated genotypes of HPV is not correlated with histopathology. By comparing our female patients' histopathological diagnosis and age, we observed that older female patients had higher-grade lesions.

Conclusions: Based on the estimated oncogenic potential of HPV genotypes as well as their prevalence in our sample, we can conclude that the nine-valent HPV vaccine for genotypes 6, 11, 16, 18, 31, 33, 45, 52, and 58 would have the potential to prevent HPV infection and the incidence of precancerous lesions and cervical cancer in about 85% of women.

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